

Synthesis of 2:6-Diethyl-4-pyrone and of 2:6-Di-*n*-propyl-4-pyrone.

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Pechmann and Neger (*Annalen*, 1893, 273, 186) have described the preparation of dehydraacetic acid and dehydrapropionyl acetic acid (II, R=CH₃ or C₂H₅) through dehydraacetocarboxylic acid and dehydrapropionyl acetocarboxylic acid respectively (I) by the action of corresponding acid chloride or anhydride on acetone dicarboxylic acid.

In the present paper this reaction has been extended to the preparation of the corresponding butyryl derivatives by using *n*-butyric anhydride or *n*-butyryl chloride (R=C₃H₇).

Further 2:6-diethyl-4-pyrone (III) which from literature does not appear to have been prepared from Pechmann and Neger's dehydra-

* Formula of Feist which has received confirmation in the hands of Rassweiler and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2758).

propionyl acetic acid has now been successfully prepared by boiling the latter with fuming hydrochloric acid.

(*cf.* preparations of corresponding dimethyl- and diphenylpyrones, Collie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 617; Feist, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3726.)

2:6-Di-*n*-propyl-4-pyrone (IV) has similarly been synthesised from dehydra-*n*-butyryl acetic acid.

The pyrones (III) and (IV) behave like dimethyl derivative in being weak monoacid bases, and in the inactivity of their carbonyl group. The pyridones corresponding to them have also been obtained. In general 2:6-disubstituted-4-pyrones change by fission of ring into 1:3:5-triketones, *e.g.*, dimethylpyrone changes into diacetylacetone (Feist, *Annalen*, 1890, 257, 276) and phenylmethylpyrone into benzoylacetylacetone (Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1283), although attempts to prepare dibenzoylacetylacetone from diphenylpyrone have failed (Feist, *Ber.*, *loc. cit.*; Ruhemann, *loc. cit.*). The pyrones (III) and (IV) have yielded the corresponding 1:3:5-triketones; but these and the velocity of transformation of such triketones back into the corresponding pyrones as affected by substituents will be the subjects for future communications.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dehydropropionyl acetocarboxylic acid, (I).—Crude acetone dicarboxylic acid (180 g.) was added in instalments and under constant stirring to propionic anhydride (500 g.) kept cool by ice-water. The temperature during addition was not allowed to rise above 10° and

the process was complete in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour when most of the acid was dissolved. The mass was then heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and on cooling poured into water. The precipitated acid after filtration and drying weighed 170 g. Pechmann and Neger (*loc. cit.*) do not mention the yield. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 114-15°.

The *monopotassium salt* of the acid was prepared by dissolving the acid in excess of aqueous caustic potash and then making strongly acid by adding acetic acid when the salt precipitated.

Dehydrapropionyl acetic acid, (I).—The monopotassium salt of the acid (1) was shaken with sufficient hot water in a flask fitted with water condenser and kept gently boiling for 40 minutes. On cooling and acidifying with acetic acid dehydrapropionyl acetic acid was precipitated which was filtered at the pump. 140 G. of dehydrapropionyl acetocarboxylic acid gave 92 g. of dehydrapropionyl acetic acid, yield 80 p.c. Pechmann and Neger's method gave a poor yield. The acid crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 72°.

2:6-*Diethyl-4 pyrone*, (III).—A mixture of dehydrapropionyl acetic acid (30 g.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19, 200 c.c.) was kept gently boiling for 4 hours. On cooling, the liquid was filtered and the bulk of the hydrochloric acid removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residual liquid was neutralised with cold caustic soda and extracted many times with ether. On drying and removing the solvent, a thin liquid remained which was distilled under reduced pressure when most of it passed between 136-38°/8 mm. On redistillation this boiled at 126°/7 mm. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 7.6. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71.0; H, 7.8 per cent.).

The pyrone is a thin liquid which freezes on cooling. The solid melts at 10°. It readily dissolves in cold water and gives no coloration with ferric chloride. It does not react with phenylhydrazine, nitrophenylhydrazine or semicarbazide.

The *hydrochloride* was prepared in the usual way. It is an extremely hygroscopic solid and can be crystallised from an excess of absolute ether from which it separates in thick prisms, m.p. 77°-78°. (Found: HCl, 19.2. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, HCl requires HCl, 19.3 per cent.).

The *chloroplatinate* is a crystalline solid, m. p. 188° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 27.4. $(C_9H_{12}O_2)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 27.3 per cent.].

The *picrate* crystallised from hot water in long yellow needles, m. p. 110°. [Found: Picric acid (by titration), 60.1. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, $C_6H_2(OH)(NO_2)_3$ requires picric acid, 60.1 per cent.].

The pyrone, like dimethylpyrone, gives with mercuric chloride a characteristic crystalline compound, crystallising from water in needles, m. p. 72° (decomp.). (Found: Hg, 47.1. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, $HgCl_2$ requires Hg, 47.5 per cent.).

2:6-Diethyl-4-pyridone.—A solution of the pyrone (3 g.) in strong ammonia (10 c.c.) was heated in a sealed tube at 130° for 4 hours. The contents were evaporated on a water-bath almost to dryness. The crude pyridone was found difficult to crystallise from any solvent. It was purified by crystallising twice from water in which it easily dissolves and from which on standing for some days it separates in thick plates, m. p. 65-66°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 8.7; N, 8.6. $C_9H_{13}ON$, H_2O requires C, 63.9; H, 8.9; N, 8.3 per cent.).

The hydrochloride melts at 76-78°. (Found: HCl, 17.7. $C_9H_{13}(ON, HCl)$, H_2O requires HCl, 17.7 per cent.).

The chloroplatinate of the pyridone was prepared as usual and crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m. p. 203° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 27.3. $(C_9H_{13}ON)_2 \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 27.3 per cent.].

Dehydrat-n-butyryl acetocarboxylic acid, (I, $R = C_3H_7$).—This was prepared from acetone dicarboxylic acid and *n*-butyric anhydride or *n*-butyryl chloride. The product obtained from butyryl chloride was purer and gave better yield than with butyric anhydride. *n*-Butyryl chloride (100 g.) was mixed with strong sulphuric acid (1.5 c.c.) and crude acetone dicarboxylic acid (30 g.) was gradually added to the liquid at room temperature. There was a vigorous evolution of hydrochloric acid gas. After all the acid was added and the vigour of the reaction subsided, the semi-solid mass was gradually heated on a water-bath. In $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the evolution of hydrochloric acid ceased and a clear red liquid was formed. On cooling this was poured on crushed ice and the precipitated acid filtered at the pump. The filtrate contained some thick red oil which after separation from the main bulk and rubbing with water gave a further crop of the acid. The acid crystallised from alcohol in thin light plates, m. p. 80°, yield 16 g. (Found: C, 58.0; H, 5.9. $C_{13}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 58.2; H, 5.9 per cent.)

The monopotassium salt of the acid crystallised from hot water in long needles, m. p. 164°. (Found: K, 12.1. $C_{13}H_{15}O_6K$ requires K, 12.6 per cent.).

Dehydratbutyryl acetic acid, (II, $R = C_3H_7$).—When the monopotassium salt described above was refluxed with water for 45 minutes and the product made acid with acetic acid, dehydratbutyryl

acetic acid separated as an oil. This was extracted with ether, dried and the solvent removed. The thick liquid which remained was distilled under reduced pressure when practically the whole passed between 140-44°/4mm. and was pure enough for analysis. 14G. of crude dehydrabutyryl acetocarboxylic acid gave 8 g. of pure dehydrabutyryl acetic acid. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 7.0. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent.).

Dehydrabutyryl acetic acid is a liquid which solidifies on cooling, melting at 16°. The acid is sparingly soluble in water and can be titrated against caustic soda with phenolphthalein as indicator. (Found: M. W. (monobasic), 223. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$ requires M. W., 224).

2:6-Di-*n*-propyl-4-pyrone, (IV).—Dehydrabutyryl acetic acid was refluxed with 10 volumes of hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) for 24 hours. On cooling a small quantity of the undissolved oil which remained was separated and the clear liquid was treated as in the preparation of diethylpyrone. The resulting liquid was distilled under reduced pressure when most of it passed between 140-42°/6 mm. This on redistillation boiled at 186°/5 mm. (Found: C, 72.9; H, 8.4. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.3; H, 8.8 per cent.).

It is an oily liquid which does not freeze even at the temperature of freezing mixture. It is sparingly soluble in hot water. The hydrochloride could not be prepared but it gave a picrate which crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 61°. [Found: Picric acid, 55.9. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$, $C_6H_2(OH)(NO_2)_3$ requires picric acid, 56.0 per cent.].

The chloroplatinate melts at 162-64°. [Found: Pt, 25.6. $(C_{11}H_{16}O_2)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 25.3 per cent.].

Like its lower homologue the pyrone forms a characteristic compound with mercuric chloride, m. p. 88-89° (decomp.). (Found: Hg, 44.6. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$, $HgCl_2$ requires Hg, 44.4 per cent.).

2:6-Di-*n*-propyl-4-pyridone.—Pure 2:6-di-*n*-propyl-4-pyrone was heated with strong ammonia in a sealed tube at 140° for 4 hours. On cooling the crystalline solid was filtered and recrystallised from hot water in long needles, m. p. 62°. This proved, as in the case of lower homologue, the hydrate of the pyridone. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 9.5; N, 6.7. $C_{11}H_{17}ON$, H_2O requires C, 67.0; H, 9.6; N, 7.1 per cent.).

The anhydrous pyridone was obtained by repeatedly extracting the hydrated pyridone with chloroform, and distilling under reduced pressure the resulting liquid left after removal of the solvent. It boiled between 210-15°/12 mm. The distillate solidified on cooling

and melted indefinitely between 85-88°. The purification of the anhydrous pyridone was met with same difficulties as in the case of its lower homologue.

The *hydrochloride* prepared in the usual way melts at 96-98°. (Found: HCl, 15.7. $C_{11}H_{17}ON$, HCl, H_2O requires HCl, 15.6 per cent.).

The *chlorplatinate* melted at 204°. [Found: Pt, 25.4. $(C_{11}H_{17}ON)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 25.4 per cent.].

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